

“ After-effect ” in certain Photochemical Reactions.

Part II.

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In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2, 227) we have shown that the phenomenon of “after-effect” is of common occurrence in photochemical reactions.

We have carried on further work in this line and have observed that the following photochemical reactions exhibit the phenomenon of after-effect: (i) ferrous sulphate and iodine; (ii) oxalic acid and iodine; (iii) sodium nitrite and iodine; (iv) the bleaching of dicyanin; (v) sodium malate and iodine; (vi) sodium formate and mercuric chloride; (vii) sodium lactate and iodine; (viii) decomposition of Fehling’s solution in presence of ferric chloride; (ix) copper sulphate and ammonium oxalate in presence of ferric chloride; (x) decomposition of potassium mangani-oxalate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the present series of experiments, with a view to obtain a more marked effect, the reacting substances were in all cases first exposed to strong sunlight.

Hollow cubes made of transparent quartz were used for these experiments. One cube containing the reacting substance was exposed to light in a thermostat, another cube was placed in the dark at the same temperature. After exposure to light for a noted interval of time the vessel was removed to darkness and the reaction velocities were determined by the usual methods. The following experimental results were obtained:—

I. *Ferrous Sulphate and Iodine.*

FeSO_4 —N/6·7; I_2 —N/90; KI —N/19·86 and H_2SO_4 —N/3. Temperature 21°.

Removed to darkness after 10 minutes' exposure to sunlight. In the dark throughout.

t (Mins.)	($a-x$) Thio- sulphate in c.c.	$K_1 \times 1/2 \cdot 3$ (Uni-mol.).	t (Mins.)	($a-x$) Thio- sulphate in c.c.	$K_1 \times 1/2 \cdot 3$ (Uni-mol.).
0	7·3	...	0	7·3	...
10	7·15	0·00090	35	7·15	0·000257
55	6·95	0·000273*	100	6·9	0·000245
135	6·65	0·000252	220	6·45	0·000244
Mean 0·000264			Mean 0·000248		

II. *Oxalic Acid and Iodine.*

Oxalic acid—N/5·192; I_2 —N/113·6 in KI —N/29·4. Temperature 32°.

Removed to darkness after 26 minutes' exposure to sunlight. In the dark throughout.

t (mins.)	($a-x$) Thio- sulphate in c.c.	$K_1 \times 1/2 \cdot 3$ (Uni-mol.).	t (mins.)	($a-x$) Thio- sulphate in c.c.	$K_1 \times 1/2 \cdot 3$ (Uni-mol.).
0	4·6	...	0	4·6	...
26	3·45	0·00481	23	4·05	0·00240
64	2·7	0·00280	38	3·75	0·00234
80	2·55	0·00243	53	3·5	0·00224
166	2·15	0·00228	84	2·96	0·00228
Mean 0·00250			Mean 0·00232		

III. *Sodium Nitrite and Iodine.*

NaNO_2 —N/1·5; I_2 —N/36·1 in KI —N/8·04 and CH_3COONa —N/6. Temperature 16°.

Exposed to sunlight for 34 minutes.

Entirely in the dark.

t (mins.)	($a-x$) Thio- sulphate in c.c.	$K_1 \times 1/2 \cdot 3$ (Uni-mol.)	t (mins.)	($a-x$) Thio- sulphate in c.c.	$K_1 \times 1/2 \cdot 3$ (Uni-mol.)
0	8·5	...	0	8·5	...
34	7·7	0·00126	50	8·3	0·000206
64	7·55	0·000287	110	8·05	0·000215
114	7·4	0·000216	170	7·8	0·000219
184	7·15	0·000215	240	7·55	0·000215
Mean 0·000239			Mean 0·000214		

* For the calculation of this and the succeeding constants, zero-time was reckoned from the moment the light was cut off. This procedure was adopted in all the following reactions.

IV. *The Bleaching of Dicyanin.*

The rate of bleaching was followed by observing at noted intervals of time the extinction coefficient of the dye by means of a Hilger-Nutting spectro-photometer.

Dicyanin—M/15,500. Temperature 16°.

Zero error—0.69 on the density scale.

Thickness of the observation cell—0.5 cm. internally.

Exposed to sun-light for 10 minutes.				Entirely in the dark.			
t (mins.)	Corrected reading on the den- sity scale.	Extinction coefficient.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.3}$ (Uni-mol.)	t (mins.)	Corrected reading on the den- sity scale.	Extinction coefficient.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.3}$ (Uni-mol.)
0	1.41	2.52	...	0	1.41	2.82	...
10	0.59	1.18	0.0378	90	0.86	1.72	0.00239
63	0.41	0.82	0.00299	140	0.66	1.32	0.00235
145	0.26	0.052	0.00245	230	0.40	0.80	0.00298
250	0.16	0.032	0.00236	270	0.32	0.64	0.00238
Mean 0.00260				Mean 0.00238			

V. *Sodium Malate and Iodine.*

Sodium malate—N/6.78; I₂—N/111.6 in KI—N/33.7. Temperature 32°.

Removed to darkness after 16 minutes' exposure to light.

In the dark throughout.

t (mins.)	(a-x) Thiosulphate in c.c.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.3}$ (Uni-mol.)	t (mins.)	(a-x) thio in c.c.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.3}$ (Uni-mol.)
0	4.95	...	0	4.95	...
16	4.2	0.00446	25	4.45	0.00185
35	3.8	0.00228	33	4.3	0.00185
55	3.5	0.00203	49	4.0	0.00189
86	3.1	0.00188	75	3.6	0.00184
124	2.65	0.00185	108	3.1	0.00188
Mean 0.00201			Mean 0.00186		

VI. *Sodium Formate and Mercuric Chloride.*

CHOONa—0.954 N; HgCl₂—N/15 and CH₃COONa—0.2613 gm. in 20 c.c. of the reacting mixture. Temperature 32°
 Removed to darkness after 20 minutes' exposure to light. In the darkness throughout.

<i>t</i> (mins.)	(<i>a-x</i>) KI in c.c.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.1}$ (Uni-mol.)	<i>t</i> (mins.)	(<i>a-x</i>) KI in c.c.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.9}$ (Uni-mol.)
0	5.78		0	5.78	...
20	4.46	0.00563	7	5.5	0.00307
38	4.04	0.00330	22	4.95	0.00306
48	3.67	0.00302	35	4.47	0.00319
68	3.15	0.00315	52	3.96	0.00316
	Mean	0.00316		Mean	0.00312

VII. *Sodium Lactate and Iodine.*

Sodium lactate—N/9.7; I₂—N/112.85 in KI—N/20.72. Temperature 32°

Exposed to light for 25 minutes.			In the dark all along.		
<i>t</i> (mins.)	(<i>a-x</i>) thio in c.c.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.9}$ (uni-mol.)	<i>t</i> (mins.)	(<i>a-x</i>) thio in c.c.	$K_1 \times \frac{1}{2.9}$ (uni-mol.)
0	1.75	—	0	1.75	—
25	1.1	0.00806	14	1.55	0.00376
38	0.95	0.00490	30	1.35	0.00376
60	0.8	0.00395	53	1.10	0.00380
85	0.65	0.00381	70	0.95	0.00379
	Mean	0.00422		Mean	0.00378

VIII. *Decomposition of Fehling's Solution in Presence of Ferric Chloride.*

No appreciable after-effect was observed in this reaction using a 500 c.p. point-to-lite lamp. This experiment was now repeated in bright sunlight and an after-effect was observed.

To 50 c.c. Fehling's solution, 0.5 c.c. dilute ferric chloride solution was added and the mixture divided into two portions. One portion was exposed to strong sunlight and another was kept in the dark. After 1½ hours' exposure to sunlight a precipitate was observed in the first case while the other remained unchanged. Now, the solution exposed to sunlight was filtered through double filter paper and the filtrate removed to darkness. In this filtrate a deposit was noticeable after 1½ hours whereas the solution kept all along in the dark did not show any precipitate whatsoever.

IX. *Copper Sulphate and Ammonium Oxalate in Presence of Ferric Chloride.*

A mixture of M/2—CuSO₄, M/21 (NH₄)₂C₂O₄ and a small quantity of FeCl₃ was made up. This was divided into two portions. One kept in the dark while the other exposed to strong sunlight. The portion exposed to light showed a red deposit in a fairly large quantity after 20 minutes. This was now carefully filtered and the filtrate removed to darkness. A deposit appeared in this filtrate after 15 minutes while in the case of the mixture all along in the dark no deposit could be noticed.

X. *The Decomposition of Potassium-mangani-oxalate.*

This compound was prepared by the method described by Christiansen (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1911, 27, 325).

Exposed to light for 2 minutes.			In the dark throughout.		
t (mins.)	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ in c.c.	K ₁ × $\frac{1}{2.3}$ (uni-molr.)	t (mins.)	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ in c.c.	K ₁ × $\frac{1}{2.3}$ (uni-molr.)
0	0.8	—	0	0.8	—
2	0.6	0.0625	4.5	0.75	0.0622
8	0.4	0.0294	14.5	0.65	0.0622
20	0.35	0.0130	26	0.55	0.0626
65	0.25	0.00603	50	0.4	0.0602
	Mean	0.0161		Mean	0.0618

It was observed by Stark (*Ann. Phys.*, 1904, 14, 520), Lord Rayleigh (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1914, 90A, 364 ; 91A, 92; 1925, 108, 262) and others that a stream of mercury vapour allowed to distil away from the arc or glow discharge in vacua remains luminous. Recently Asterblum (*Z. Physik*, 1927, 43, 427) has shown that the duration of after-glow of mercury decreases in intensity logarithmically with time. This persistence of the glow in mercury and the phenomenon of after-effect as observed in photochemical reactions appear to be identical.

Wood (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1921, 99, 362) has come to the conclusion that though the normal life-period of activated atoms and molecules

is of the order 10^{-6} seconds, in some cases the life-period can be considerably prolonged and in several cases it comes out to be of the order 10^{-6} .

We are also of the opinion that the life-period of the activated molecules in photochemical reactions taking place in solution is considerably prolonged. The gradual vanishing of the influence of the activated molecules just after removal of the reacting system from light to darkness is evident by a concomitant decrease in the velocity of the reaction till it has the same value as that obtained in the reaction taking place all along in the dark. Recently Eggert and his coworkers (*Z. Physik*, 1925, 26, 865) have stated that excited bromine molecules have a relatively long life-period and is possibly of the order of 10^{-5} sec. We are of the opinion that the life-period of the activated molecules in the photochemical reaction taking place in solution is considerably prolonged and the slow reversion of the activated molecules into the inactive state is the main cause of the phenomenon of after-effect.

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